

ASSESSMENT OF SUBOPTIMAL BIRTH INTERVAL (SOBI) ON SELECTED MATERNAL AND NEWBORN OUTCOME AMONG MOTHERS AND NEWBORNS ADMITTED IN LABOR WARD OF SELECTED HOSPITALS OF THE CITY

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This research was approved by institutional ethics committee of Sinhgad College of nursing, pune. The written consent was taken from participants. The information given from the participants was kept confidential and use extensively for the benefit of the profession.

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Authors' contribution:

All authors were involved in research planning. All authors collected sample subjects, measured, and analysed data, and prepare the original manuscript draft. All authors read and approved final manuscript.

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Abstract

Background: Suboptimal Birth Interval (SOBI) negatively affects maternal and neonatal health. This study aimed to evaluate its impact on selected maternal and newborns outcomes among mothers admitted to labor wards.

Objectives:

- (1) To assess maternal outcomes.
- (2) To assess newborns outcomes.
- (3) To examine associations between maternal and newborns outcomes.
- (4) To identify associations with selected demographic variables.

Methods: A quantitative, cross-sectional observational study was conducted among 150 mothers selected through convenience sampling from selected hospitals. Data collection was carried out from 24/12/2024–01/01/2025 and 01/02/2025–20/02/2025. Maternal outcomes were assessed using a self-structured tool on Days 1–3, while newborns outcomes were measured on Day 1 using APGAR scores and anthropometric parameters.

Results: Maternal outcomes significantly improved from Day 1 to Day 3 ($p < 0.05$). At 1 minute, 98.7% of newborns were moderately depressed, with improvement by 5 minutes (82.7% excellent APGAR scores). However, abnormal anthropometric measurements were observed in 82.7% of newborns. No significant association was found between maternal and newborn outcomes or with demographic variables.

Conclusion: SOBI increases risks for both mothers and newborns. Promotion of optimal birth spacing is essential to improve maternal recovery and neonatal health outcomes.

Keywords: Assessment; Suboptimal Birth Interval (SOBI); maternal outcome; Newborn outcome; Labor.

Introduction:

Birth spacing, defined as the interval between two consecutive live births, is a critical determinant of maternal, newborn, and child health. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends an optimal interval of 33–59 months, while a short birth interval (<33 months) is associated with increased risks of adverse outcomes, including preterm birth, low birth weight, anemia, preeclampsia, and maternal mortality. Adequate spacing allows mothers to recover physically and nutritionally from pregnancy, childbirth, and breastfeeding, thereby reducing complications and improving survival rates.¹

Globally, appropriate birth spacing could prevent up to 25% of maternal and child deaths. Despite its recognized importance, many women continue to have shorter intervals due to factors such as low education, limited access to family planning, and sociocultural influences. Promoting optimal birth spacing remains a key strategy in reproductive health programs to enhance maternal well-being and child survival.²

Previous research indicates that insufficient birth spacing may be associated with increased risks such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and maternal complications. Understanding these potential consequences is critical to improving prenatal care and developing strategies to improve maternal and fetal well-being. This study aims to provide valuable information by

examining the specific effects of optimal birth spacing in a selected hospital and delivery department context. Birth spacing is key in ensuring the health of mothers and their children as well as determining population growth. Most of the mothers in developing nations including Ethiopia have been practicing short inter-birth intervals. There is a paucity of studies concerned with suboptimal birth spacing among women of reproductive age in the study area.³

Close birth increases the risk of adverse consequences for the health of the mother and child. In Ethiopia, the prevalence of short birth spacing varied widely between different studies. Additionally, contraceptive use, educational level, and duration of breastfeeding were frequently cited as factors affecting short birth intervals.⁴

Methods:

The present study adopted a quantitative research approach with a cross-sectional observational design to assess the impact of suboptimal birth interval on maternal and newborn outcomes. The study was conducted at selected hospitals in the city. Data was collected from 24/12/2024–01/01/2025 and 01/02/2025–20/02/2025. The target population included mothers and newborns admitted to the labor wards of these hospitals, and a total of 150 samples were selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. The sample size was calculated using the power analysis formula-

$$n = (Z_{\alpha/2})^2 * p * (1-p) / MOE^2$$

Where, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the critical value of the normal distribution at $\alpha/2$ (e.g. for a confidence level of 95%, α is 0.05 and the critical value is 1.96)

MOE is the margin of error

p is the prevalence

For my calculations,

$$Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$$

$$P = 0.599$$

$$MOE = 0.08$$

$$n = (1.96)^2 * 0.599 * (1 - 0.599) / (0.08)^2$$

$$= 3.8416 * 0.599 * (1 - 0.599) / 0.0064$$

$$= 2.301 * 0.401 / 0.0064$$

$$= 0.922 / 0.0064$$

$$= 144.06$$

The sample size, n comes to be 144. So, Sample size is 150

The inclusion criteria comprised women with multiparity, singleton pregnancy, and those admitted in active labor or undergoing induction of labor, who were willing to participate in the study. The exclusion criteria included women with pre-existing medical conditions such as chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, or bad obstetric history, those undergoing elective cesarean section without labor, and primiparous women. Participants also retained the right to withdraw from the study at any point during data collection. For data collection, a structured tool was prepared consisting of three parts: Part I – informed consent form, Part II – demographic variables, and Part III – a self-structured tool for maternal assessment and a standardized tool for newborn assessment. The data analysis plan involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage distribution

were used to describe demographic variables, while mean, median, mode, standard deviation, range, and percentiles were applied to variables related to birth intervals, maternal outcomes (e.g., complications, mode of delivery), and newborn outcomes (e.g., birth weight, Apgar scores). For inferential analysis, a paired t-test was used to examine changes in maternal outcomes over day 1, day 2, and day 3, while Fisher's exact test was employed to identify associations between study findings and selected demographic variables.

Result:

A total of 150 mothers admitted to labour wards participated in the study. The majority (66%) were aged 27.1–36 years, 52.7% were homemakers, and 40% had a monthly income of less than ₹20,000. More than half (54.7%) had one living child, and 85.3% reported a birth interval of 1–3 years. Most mothers (75.3%) were at 34.1–38 weeks of gestation. Regarding previous deliveries, 62% had undergone caesarean section, and 44% had experienced anaemia during their last labour.

On Day 1, 76% of mothers had mild maternal outcomes and 24% moderate. By Day 3, 98% had mild outcomes and only 2% moderate, with no severe cases across all days. (Table.1)

A paired t-test showed significant improvement in maternal outcomes from Day 1 (Mean = 4.91, SD = 1.95) to Day 2 (Mean = 3.83, SD = 1.82; $t = 5.38$, $p < 0.001$) and Day 3 (Mean = 3.27, SD = 2.20; $t = 7.67$, $p < 0.001$) (Table.2).

Day-wise analysis of clinical parameters revealed progressive improvement in postpartum haemorrhage, thromboembolic signs, fundal height, uterine tone, lochia odour, and fever between Day 1 and Day 3.

At one minute after birth, 98.7% of newborns were moderately depressed on the APGAR scale, with only 0.7% each in severe depression and excellent condition. At five minutes, 82.7% had shifted to excellent condition and 17.3% remained moderately depressed (Table.3).

Anthropometric assessment showed that 82.7% of newborns had abnormal measurements and only 17.3% were normal (Table.4)

Fisher's exact test showed no statistically significant association between maternal outcomes and neonatal outcomes (APGAR at 1 and 5 min, anthropometric measurements). No significant associations were found between demographic characteristics and neonatal APGAR scores at one minute, anthropometric measurements, or maternal outcomes.

Discussion:

The study aimed to assess the impact of Suboptimal Birth Interval (SOBI) on maternal and newborn outcomes among mothers and newborns admitted to labor wards in selected hospitals. The findings indicate that a majority of the mothers belonged to the age group of 27.1-36 years, with homemakers being the dominant occupational category. A significant proportion of mothers had a birth interval of 1 to 3 years, and cesarean delivery was more prevalent in previous pregnancies. Additionally, a considerable number of mothers had experienced maternal complications such as postpartum hemorrhage, infections, and anemia in their last labor. Regarding maternal outcomes, the study found a significant improvement in maternal health over three days post-delivery. On day one, a substantial proportion of mothers experienced mild to moderate effects. However, by day three, the majority exhibited only mild effects, suggesting a progressive recovery. The paired t-test confirmed a statistically significant improvement in maternal outcomes over time, demonstrating a positive trend in postpartum recovery. Newborn outcomes, evaluated using APGAR scores and anthropometric measurements, highlighted concerning trends. At one minute post-birth, a high percentage of newborns were moderately depressed, although this improved significantly by the five-minute mark. However, an alarming finding was that a majority of newborns (82.7%) exhibited abnormal anthropometric measurements, which may suggest potential concerns related to suboptimal birth intervals or other maternal factors influencing fetal growth and development. When assessing the association between maternal and newborn outcomes, no significant relationships were identified, indicating that maternal health status did not directly affect neonatal outcomes in this study. Similarly, demographic variables such as age, occupation, income, and number of previous children did not show any significant association with maternal outcomes, newborn APGAR scores, or anthropometric measurements. This suggests that while individual characteristics might influence health outcomes, their direct statistical significance was not established in this study. Overall, the findings emphasize the need for further research on the implications of SOBI on maternal and neonatal health. While maternal outcomes showed a clear pattern of improvement post-delivery, concerns remain regarding neonatal health, particularly anthropometric measurements. Interventions promoting optimal birth spacing and improved prenatal care may help mitigate risks associated with suboptimal birth intervals, thereby improving both maternal and newborn health outcomes. Many studies, including those by Abebaw Abeje Muluneh, Zemenu Yohannes Kassa, and others, have identified a link between short birth spacing and adverse maternal and child health outcomes, such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and increased mortality risks.⁵ Holendro Singh Chungkham and Harihar Sahoo's research in 2020 specifically highlighted that longer birth intervals lead to better health and nutritional outcomes for both mothers and children. Studies from Ethiopia also found that a short birth interval is associated with adverse perinatal, maternal, and infant outcomes.⁶

Conclusion:

The study demonstrated that maternal outcomes improved significantly from Day 1 to Day 3 of postpartum observation, with reductions in complications such as postpartum haemorrhage, thromboembolic signs, uterine tone abnormalities, lochia odour, and fever. Similarly, newborn outcomes improved, as reflected in higher APGAR scores at five minutes compared to one minute after birth. Although the majority of newborns had abnormal anthropometric measurements, no significant associations were found between maternal and neonatal outcomes or between these outcomes and selected demographic variables. These findings highlight the importance of close monitoring of mothers and newborns in the immediate

postpartum period to ensure early identification and management of complications. Strengthening postnatal care services and promoting adequate birth intervals may contribute to better maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

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Tables:

Table 1: Maternal outcome among mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals

n=150

Maternal outcome	Day1		Day2		Day3	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild	114	76.0%	131	87.3%	147	98.0%
Moderate	36	24.0%	19	12.7%	3	2.0%
Severe	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%

Table 2: Paired t-test for the change in maternal outcome among mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals over day1, day2 and day3

n=150

Timepoint	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
Day1	4.91	1.95			
Day2	3.83	1.82	5.38	149	0.000
Day3	3.27	2.20	7.67	149	0.000

Table 3: Newborn outcome among newborn of mothers admitted in labour ward based on APGAR score

n=150

Time	Newborn condition	Freq	%
1 min	Severely depressed	1	0.7%
	Moderately depressed	148	98.7%
	Excellent condition	1	0.7%
5 min	Severely depressed	0	0.0%
	Moderately depressed	26	17.3%
	Excellent condition	124	82.7%

Table 4: Newborn outcome among newborn of mothers admitted in labour ward based on anthropometric measurements

n=150

Anthropometric measurement	Freq	%
Normal	26	17.3%
Abnormal	124	82.7%

Abbreviations:

SOBI: Suboptimal birth interval

BI: Birth interval